

Terminologies in Silappadhikaram

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Abstract

Musical Terminologies are the special words or the special Language used by the Musicians which are specific to Music. As the Herò or Heròine of Silappadhikāram were singers and Experts in Yāzh, the Music Terminologies are found in abundant in Silappadhikāram. They are found in the form of Pan, Pālai, Musical Instruments, Musical Compositions and so on.

Keywords: Ilangò Adigal, Technical Terms, Pan, Pālai, Aalathi, Musical Forms, Vari, Tālam, Singing Techniques, Playing Techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Silappadhikāram written by Saint IlangòAdigal is one of the five major Epics of the Tamil Literature. It is a treasure house contains mine of information regarding Music and Dance that depicts the Art, Culture, and the Life of the Ancient Tamil People. Born from a Royal Family Ilangò Adigal with multiple skills well versed in many Arts. This Silappadhikāram portrays his multidimensional knowledge about many subjects. One of such artistic skill is Music. The main Herò (Kòvalan) and Heròine (Mādavi) were Singers and Experts in Music and Yāzh. Through them Ilangò Adigal explores Music in Depth.

Terminology

They are the special words that are used in a particular profession, subject. It is the Language used to describe a specific thing or the Language used within a specific field. They are the Technical Terms used in Business, Arts, Science, or Special subjects. Special Language used by scientists is an example of Science Terminology. Special Unique Language used by experts in Music is Music Terminology. As Kòvalan and Mādavi were experts in Music, Music Technical Terms are found abundantly in Silappadhikāram.

Music Terminology

They are the Unique Technical Terms specific to Music. There are more than 100 Unique Terms seen in Silappadhikāram with respect to Music. They are in the form of Pan name, Pālai name, Singing Techniques, Playing (Yāzh), Techniques, Musical Compositions, Musical Instruments, Tala aspects and so on.

Terminology Used in Pan

They are the Terms used for present Ragas in Karnātic Music

- 1) Pālaippan
- 2) Kurunjippan
- 3) Marudappan
- 4) Kowsigappan
- 5) Nōthiram
- 6) Aāsanthiram
- 7) Seegāmaram
- 8) Thōdi
- 9) Gandhāram
- 10) Sendhurutthi
- 11) Aāmbal
- 12) Panniam - Pan with 6 notes
- 13) Thiram- Pan with 5 notes

Classification of Pan

- 14) Arugu
- 15) Aganilai
- 16) Arugial
- 17) Perugu
- 18) Puram
- 19) Agam

Terminology in Pālai

They are the Musical Scales

- 20) Aāyappālai - Linear Musical Scales
- 21) Chadurappālai - Musical Scales in Square
- 22) Tirikōnappālai - Musical Scales in Triangular
- 23) Vattappālai - Musical Scales in Circles

Terminology in Aālathi

They are the melodic improvisations while singing

- 24) Katālathi
- 25) Pannālathi
- 26) Niravālathi

Terminology in Musical Forms

They are the simple songs about river, sea, and some group folk songs sung by girls while playing. They are called Vari

- 27) Kānal Vari
- 28) Aātru Vari
- 29) Vettuva Vari
- 30) Sāththu Vari
- 31) Nilai Vari
- 32) Mugamil Vari
- 33) Muri Vari
- 34) ThinaiNilai Vari
- 35) Sāyal Vari
- 36) MayangunilaiThinai Vari
- 37) Kanduga Vari
- 38) Usal Vari
- 39) Ammānai Vari

Terminology in Tālam

They are the words pertaining to Tālam either parts of the Tālam or action pertaining to Tālam.

- 40) Asai
- 41) Alavu
- 42) Seer
- 43) Iyakkam
- 44) Mātthirai
- 45) Thākkku
- 46) Thiral
- 47) Kottu

Terminology in Singing Techniques

- 48) Alagu - pitch intervals between Notes
- 49) SariraVinai – Voice
- 50) Inai – parallel Octave
- 51) Isai Ezhāl - production of melody
- 52) Edutthal - Singing Technique
- 53) Kēlvi – hearing Musical note
- 54) Kilai – a relative note
- 55) Kurai - deficiency
- 56) Kural Thiribu – Shift of Tonic
- 57) Kudam - dissonance
- 58) Mandalam – a circle
- 59) Mandham- lower note
- 60) Melivu -slender note
- 61) Murai – order
- 62) Mudivu - end
- 63) Natpu - Friend – Fourth note
- 64) Nirai - full
- 65) Niram – colour
- 66) Pagai - enemy – dissonance note
- 67) Pan nīrmai - Characteristic of the Pan

Terminology and Musical Instruments

Yāzh

Specific new Terms are used for the parts of the Yāzh and playing Techniques

- 68) AādhīYāzh - A Yāzh with 1000 Strings
- 69) Aāni - Part of Yāzh (peg)
- 70) Kōdu - Part of Yāzh
- 71) Mādagam – Part of Yāzh
- 72) Ottruruppu – Part of Yāzh
- 73) Narambu – a String
- 74) Patthar- a part of Yāzh
- 75) Thiravu – a part of Yāzh
- 76) Viral - Fingers

- 77) Padutthal - A playing Technique
- 78) Thaivaral - A playing Technique
- 79) Theruvaral - A playing Technique
- 80) Urazhdhal - A playing Technique
- 81) Undhal - A playing Technique
- 82) Uruttal - A playing Technique
- 83) Vārdhal - A playing Technique
- 84) pattadai - A playing Technique
- 85) kurumbòkku - A playing Technique
- 86) pannal - A playing Technique
- 87) parivattanai - A playing Technique
- 88) karanam - A playing Technique
- 89) Kaiyùzh - A playing Technique
- 90) Allal - A playing Technique
- 91) Idamurai – Anti clock wise – method

Flute

- 92) Aāmbal - a flute
- 93) Aimpuzhai Kuzhal – Flute with 5 holes
- 94) Anaису – Metal Rim around the left tip of flute
- 95) Chitthirappunarppu – playing Techniques
- 96) Muddhirai - The Hole in flute close to right End
- 97) Thùmbu mugam - Left End of the flute
- 98) Vanjanai punarppu - playing Technique
- 99) Vartthanai - playing Technique

Percussion Instruments

- 100) Aāmandirikai - a percussion Instruments
- 101) Adakkai - playing Technique
- 102) Kottu - Drum syllable
- 103) Kunil - Stick used for Drumming
- 104) Vācchiyam - Drum
- 105) Aga muzhavu - A percussion Instrument
- 106) Aāvanchi – A percussion Instrument

CONCLUSION

Silappadhikāram delineates the outstanding musical knowledge of the Tamil People in second Century. From these Musical Terminologies we understand that they were well versed in Music and Yāzh. This Musical Terminologies conveys in-depth knowledge of the author towards Music. Pan and Pālai system shows his extraordinary brilliance in this Special Art.

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